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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Historians and archaeologists Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Document or Monitor

Methods for Collecting or Accessing Digital

Challenges in Using Technologies

Historians and archaeologists Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Historians and archaeologists Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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Historians and archaeologists 3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Historians and archaeologists Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Historians and archaeologist.

Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	Textual sources (manuscripts, inscriptions, archival records)	Images (photographs, maps, drawings)	3D models (artifacts, architectural reconstructions)	Geospatial data (maps, excavation plans, coordinates)	Stratigraphic data (e.g., excavation units, US forms)	Scientific data (e.g., dating analysis, material composition)	Audio and video materials (oral history, recorded interviews, site videos)	Linked Open Data or structured metadata	Tabular datasets (e.g., CSV, spreadsheets)
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	32	39	26	37	27	27	11	12	21
3D modeling or virtual reconstruction software	22	27	25	23	16	19	9	7	12
Digital image analysis (e.g., remote sensing, satellite imagery)	17	21	13	18	17	15	5	4	13
Digital text analysis or annotation tools (e.g., OCR, TEI/XML editors)	22	23	13	16	9	18	6	9	13
Linked Open Data platforms or semantic web tools	16	18	11	17	9	17	7	14	16
Digital archives or heritage databases	40	45	26	35	25	34	13	16	22
Photogrammetry tools	16	22	20	21	16	16	6	6	11
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	12	16	14	13	10	11	3	2	5
Data visualization tools (e.g., network analysis, timelines)	20	22	14	18	13	17	5	8	15
I don't use digital tools	3	3	1	2	2	1	2	0	2

TECHNOLOGIES × METHODS	Fieldwork (e.g., excavation, surveys, on-site documentation)	Archival or library research	Digital repositories or online databases	Remote sensing and aerial/satellite imagery	Collaboration with scientific labs or specialists	Manual data entry or digitization of physical sources	Data reused from previous projects
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	33	31	31	20	22	21	25
3D modeling or virtual reconstruction software	25	23	17	14	14	13	15
Digital image analysis (e.g., remote sensing, satellite imagery)	15	16	14	15	10	14	10
Digital text analysis or annotation tools (e.g., OCR, TEI/XML editors)	12	20	19	9	9	14	18
Linked Open Data platforms or semantic web tools	11	18	18	6	7	12	16
Digital archives or heritage databases	32	41	35	17	22	24	28
Photogrammetry tools	22	18	15	14	12	11	14
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	16	12	8	8	9	7	9
Data visualization tools (e.g., network analysis, timelines)	14	18	15	8	11	12	16
I don't use digital tools	1	2	3	0	1	1	1

MONITORING TOOLS × USING CHALLENGES	Lack of technical training or expertise	Lack of dedicated digital tools for fieldwork or site documentation	High cost of tools, software, or equipment	Fragmentation of data across different platforms or formats	Limited time/resources for digital documentation	Difficulties integrating digital workflows with traditional research practices	Institutional or project-level limitations (e.g., lack of support, policy issues)	I don't experience particular difficulties
GIS systems or remote sensing platforms	24	18	21	26	21	18	20	2
Drone-based survey or mapping tools	13	7	13	10	10	8	12	1
Environmental sensors for site monitoring	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	1
Survey equipment (e.g., GPS, total stations)	16	13	17	20	14	13	15	2
I do not use digital tools for surveying or monitoring	12	4	5	6	4	5	4	1

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Text documents (PDF, Word, TEI/XML)	Tabular data (CSV, Excel)	Relational database formats (e.g., Microsoft Access, MySQL, PostgreSQL)	Geospatial formats (GeoTIFF, SHP, KML)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Multimedia formats (e.g., JPEG, MP4, WAV)	Structured metadata or semantic web data (e.g., RDF, JSON-LD)
Textual sources (manuscripts, inscriptions, archival records)	43	39	19	24	19	30	9
Images (photographs, maps, drawings)	50	44	21	30	26	37	10
3D models (artifacts, architectural reconstructions)	26	23	14	18	24	22	6
Geospatial data (maps, excavation plans, coordinates)	37	34	19	30	24	31	9
Stratigraphic data (e.g., excavation units, US forms)	28	25	15	22	17	22	6
Scientific data (e.g., dating analysis, material composition)	32	32	18	21	20	25	10
Audio and video materials (oral history, recorded interviews, site videos)	15	11	6	8	6	13	7
Linked Open Data or structured metadata	14	14	9	8	7	9	9
Tabular datasets (e.g., CSV, spreadsheets)	24	25	14	19	15	17	9

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing	Lack of adequate digital infrastructure for data storage and access	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Limited collaboration or openness in the research community	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	13	11	15	9	7	3
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., GitHub, ARK, OpenContext)	5	6	6	3	6	0
No, but I'd be interested in using them	5	9	8	13	7	2
No, I don't see their usefulness	1	0	1	1	1	2

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of technical skills or training	Difficulty aligning digital workflows with traditional methods	Fragmentation of digital and non-digital sources	Lack of institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to change among peers or institutions	No significant difficulties
Yes, frequently	10	8	11	9	6	2
Yes, occasionally	19	12	18	16	16	2
No, but I would be interested	10	3	6	6	3	2
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	2	2	1	0	0

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Improved documentation and visualization of sites and artifacts	Enhanced analysis and interpretation of historical contexts	Facilitation of interdisciplinary research and data integration	Simulation of historical developments or reconstructions	Support for educational and public engagement	I do not see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	12	7	7	12	11	1
Yes, occasionally	21	23	16	17	19	1
No, but I would be interested	11	10	9	7	11	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	2	0	1	2	1

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of technical skills or training	Difficulty aligning digital workflows with traditional methods	Fragmentation of digital and non-digital sources	Lack of institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to change among peers or institutions	No significant difficulties
Yes, frequently	3	0	3	0	1	1
Yes, occasionally	12	12	15	12	15	1
No, but I would be interested	25	12	18	19	9	3
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	1	1	1	0	1

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Spatial and topographical data (e.g., GIS, site maps, terrain models)	Historical documentation (e.g., archival texts, ancient maps, historical images)	Stratigraphic and chronological data (e.g., excavation layers, dating sequences)	Environmental and climatic data (e.g., erosion, vegetation, water tables)	Simulations of human activities, events, or settlement patterns	Alerts and sensor data for real-time site monitoring	Interoperable metadata to support integration with external datasets	Collaborative tools for multi-institutional research
Yes, frequently	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2
Yes, occasionally	23	20	17	19	16	15	9	11
No, but I would be interested	28	28	23	17	20	8	15	17
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	3	3	2	0	0	0	1	0